

Integrating flexibility and energy local markets with wholesale balancing responsibilities in the context of renewable energy communities

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ABSTRACT

Prosumers can organize themselves in collective self-consumption (CSC) structures and renewable energy communities (REC) to share energy they produce locally. In addition, through their contracted balancing responsible parties (BRP), i.e., retailers (RET) and aggregators (AGR), they could become flexibility providers for system services to solve, for example, local grid constraints. Since CSC and REC structures are progressively being regulated in many countries, local energy markets (LEM) and local flexibility markets (LFM) to be developed with these structures should find the way to comply with existing CSC rules to settle energy transactions and flexibility activation, both, locally and with the wholesale (WS) market settlement, or the existing barriers and regulatory improvements identified to allow future implementations. Indeed, the integration of local and wholesale electricity markets is still a matter of development, demanding innovative solutions, one of the main issues being, for example, the impact of the flexibility activation by one BRP into another BRP's expected delivery commitment in the WS market. This work proposes innovative designs for LEM and LFM based on common CSC rules of existing regulations, and a conceptual approach to integrate them together and with the WS market balancing responsibilities of the BRPs involved, identifying existing regulatory barriers. While many LEM in the literature operate as WS markets, with future markets and delivery commitments for prosumers, we propose the use of a post-delivery LEM that can be cleared even after the delivery of energy, which strongly simplifies prosumers participation avoiding the need of these a priori unrealistic commitments. The business model, the main roles involved and the contractual framework to connect the BRPs while allowing prosumers to freely contract the BRP of their choice for both energy supply and flexibility provision, are described, and can serve as a guide for future regulatory improvement of the common regulatory frameworks.

ABBREVIATIONS

AC – Allocation Coefficients

AGR – Aggregators

ARP – Allocation Responsible Party

BRP – Balancing Responsible Party

BSP – Balancing Service Provider

CSC – Collective Self-consumption

DER – Distributed Energy Resources

DSO – Distribution System Operator

EU – European Union

FRP – Flexibility Requesting Party

ISC – Individual Self-consumption

ISP – Imbalance Settlement Periods

LEM – Local Energy Market

LFM – Local Flexibility Market

LFMO – Local Flexibility Market Operator

MDC – Metering Data Company

P2P – Peer to Peer

REC – Renewable Energy Community

RET – Retailers

TSO – Transmission System Operator

WSM – Wholesale Market

1. INTRODUCTION

The EU carbon neutrality goal by 2050 proposes several energy policy strategies, including the increase of renewable generation, empowerment of consumers and decentralizing the energy generation [1]. These goals require regulatory and market design innovations, especially considering the need to provide prosumers with new tools to engage in energy

trading and sharing schemes. The EU Directive 2018/2001 [2] and EU Directive 2019/944 [3] define the concepts and roles of individual self-consumption (ISC), CSC, REC, and introduces the concept of peer-to-peer (P2P) direct trading between local markets' participants. These directives also state that CSC and P2P markets should allow prosumers to trade locally with their peers while maintaining their supply contracts with their RET, so they can buy from the grid any energy not internally supplied, or alternatively, sell to an AGR their remaining energy surplus after the local sharing. The very recent EU market reform proposal [4] goes further by stating that end consumers should have the right to share renewable energy directly, without the need of creating energy communities, reducing barriers and incentivizing even more the development of self-consumption structures to engage customers as active participants of the energy system.

Member states are currently transposing these directives to their own national regulations [5]. For example, Spain [6], France [7], and Portugal [8] have adopted similar CSC sharing mechanisms, based on allocation coefficients (AC) that are used by the DSO to allocate energy among prosumers [9]. Dynamic AC (detailed below), not allowed in all regulations, but explicitly considered in the recent EU market reform proposal [4], are computed by the REC manager after the energy delivery to properly share energy among prosumers for each Imbalance Settlement Period (ISP) according to their agreed internal rules. The use of dynamic AC effectively integrates the LEM settlement with the wholesale market (WSM) settlement, since local transactions are transposed into WSM BRP to BRP energy transfers, [10], as explained in this work. Considering this property, innovative LEM such as the post-delivery LEM proposed in [11] that allows LEM trades to occur even after the delivery of the energy, become possible. Local transactions can be incorporated into the CSC allocation of energy by using the AC that directly impact both RET and AGR WSM positions, and thus, their balance responsibilities [9]. This is also essential to LEM, since it avoids improper billing to the LEM participants by the BRP with which they interact, i.e., RET and AGR. The reviewed literature found proposals of REC management that considers dynamic AC defined after the delivery the energy sharing [12], [13]. A dynamic AC based LEM was proposed in [14], but LEM contracts are forward and prosumers are financially punished for not delivering the committed delivery. Post-delivery LEM has been simulated as a pricing mechanism in [15], but not integrated with LFM markets.

When dealing with flexibility at the local level, LFM, LEM and WSM settlement can and should also be properly integrated. For example, [16], [17] report on the importance of dealing with the transfer of energy between AGR and RET when local flexibility is delivered to avoid situations where the AGR profits from the existing flexibility at the expense of RET potential imbalances. It also has the advantage of effectively allocating the delivered flexibility to the AGR who can then settle it in the WSM with the Flexibility Requesting Party (FRP). This requires a contracting framework that, among other matters, defines the baseline for setting the delivery commitment of the distributed energy resources (DER) that allows their BRPs to compute the delivered flexibility to the FRP. LFM designs should consider these issues, since, as already said, the activation of flexibility by an AGR can impact a third party BRP's portfolio, such as the RET of the customer providing flexibility to the AGR by generating potential imbalances corresponding to the flexibility activated, to which the RET could react by increasing its energy selling tariffs to compensate these potential imbalances. This means that both RET and AGR wholesale market positions are interrelated, and agreements could be arranged to compensate for these potential imbalances.

The reviewed LFM literature shows a lack of LFM proposals that tackle, in a practical way, how to solve this issue of the transfer of activated flexibility energy from AGR to RET. Of the several models proposed in [17], the so-called contractual model assumes a framework contractual agreement between AGR and RET and other parties, which defines a methodology to compute the baseline used by all parties for flexibility delivery verification. However, the way to operationalize this contract in the setting of the energy communities and integrated with the current CSC regulation is not addressed.

Under this context of LEM, LFM, WSM and their many interactions, the main contribution of this paper is the proposal of a dual LFM and post-delivery LEM design that uses CSC allocation rules (for both CSC structures or energy communities) based on dynamic AC, see [3] and [9], for its integration within the WSM settlement. While the post-delivery LEM, based on [11], [18], allows to trade energy locally even after delivery, without the need of forecasting, participating in LFM requires that the AGR computes the baseline for verification purposes. Regarding the baseline, it is necessary that the AGR and the distribution system operator (DSO) agree on a methodology to compute the baseline for verification purposes. Indeed, the main issue in unifying LFM and post-delivery LEM is on the fact that flexibility contracts must have delivery commitments, while the post-delivery energy contracts don't. Therefore, a solution based on a framework contract agreed between the AGR, RET and all other parties involved in the flexibility products, including the FRP, is proposed, where each agent roles and responsibilities are defined, mainly regarding the baseline and the use of dynamic AC to settle the energy transfers. The proposal is done at a conceptual level and is coherent with the current regulation for self-consumption being developed in several European countries. It provides a simple market environment where peers may easily trade the energy generated locally while in full integration with the parties involved in wholesale balance responsibility and flexibility contracts, such as the RET, AGR, DSO and other FRP.

The LFM proposal assumes that a framework contract under the LFM rules is agreed by all the above cited stakeholders, where the baseline is crucial to compute the delivered flexibility as the difference between the actual delivery and the baseline, just like a derivative contract where the baseline is the volumetric reference asset [19]. While most of the LFM

literature assumes the use of a baseline, with several methods to compute baseline on LFM and the claim of the importance of standardizing it [16], reference [21] states that baseline assumptions for LFM are inefficient, leading to “unnecessary uncertainty, administrative burden, risks and potential conflicts of interest between the different stakeholders”. Therefore, they propose the use of capacity limits, where DER must operate within a load limit, leading, according to the authors, to more efficient LFM for some limited flexibility needs, like DSO load containment. However, some sort of baseline method is still needed to measure the energy delivered if these LFM products propose a solution to the transfer of energy problem. As also reviewed on [14] and [16], most LFM research and real application projects make use of baselines since it is compatible with wholesale balancing markets and BRP positions. However, although we assume the existence of a baseline methodology, further baseline concerns or developments fall out of the scope of this work.

The integrated post-delivery LEM and LFM proposal also assumes that the framework contract of the LFM is compatible with the several possible flexibility services required by wholesale stakeholders. For instance, any wholesale FRP may require LFM flexibility, including DSO, transmission system operator (TSO), BRPs for any of the several types of services they might need [23], [24], if the baseline is accepted by them for the verification of the actual flexibility provision and the participation of distributed flexibility is properly regulated.

Therefore, the main contributions of this work are:

- A dual LFM & post-delivery LEM conceptual design where a post-delivery energy market and a LFM are integrated together and within the WSM settlement rules by using the existing self-consumption regulation.
- The revision of the main actor roles of the markets’ participants.
- A LFM design that uses the recent CSC regulation under development in the EU to provide a practical way to transfer energy between WSM BRP, with simple and limited enhancements of the common current self-consumption regulation.
- The definition of a contractual framework to properly manage the balancing responsibilities of the markets’ participants, reducing their imbalance risks, by integrating the energy transfers of the activated flexibility between AGR and RET using regular LEM energy transfers that could be easily supported by the CSC regulation. As said, limited regulatory enhancements are identified and proposed for full framework support.

Following this introduction, section 2 introduces the main flexibility concepts used in the paper, the potential capability of CSC structures and energy communities to provide flexibility, and the associated energy transfer problem that motivates this work. Section 3 reviews the common approach used to regulate CSC structures, including the use of AC to allocate energy internally among the self-consumption members, and the impact of this allocation on the WSM settlement and on the BRPs positions. Section 4 reviews the post-delivery LEM design, and how its transactions are integrated with the WSM after the DER production and consumption occur, including the proposed framework for this integration and to solve the transfer of energy problem. Finally, section 5 concludes this paper.

2. LOCAL FLEXIBILITY MARKETS AND THE ENERGY TRANSFER PROBLEM

Flexibility has several possible definitions, but commonly refers to the possibility of modifying generation and/or consumption patterns in reaction to an external signal to contribute to the power system [23]. When these signals are prices or tariffs, flexibility is known as implicit flexibility, as opposed to explicit flexibility that results from an explicit activation signal [16]. Local flexibility markets are markets where explicit flexibility is traded and whose participants are limited to a geographical area like communities, neighborhoods or on a larger scope, for example, a distribution grid zone [25]. These markets help to unlock the flexibility from distributed energy resources to provide, for example, grid services and therefore facilitate the integration of renewable generation and avoid or postpone traditional network investments [26]. Although not yet regulated, it is commonly accepted that LFM, in coordination with existing TSO flexibility markets, will be an essential tool for the energy transition, since traditional flexibility provider resources are being decommissioned or will remain just as punctual support but with limited availability [23].

In general, distributed flexibility within a CSC and REC structures can have multiple uses as described in Figure 1, where both, implicit and explicit flexibility are represented. As can be seen, distributed flexibility could be used for the internal balance of the CSC structure, for BRPs balancing in energy adjustment markets (intraday markets), or for system services in TSO or DSO services markets (see [27] for a review of TSO and DSO flexibility needs and flexibility coordination schemes).

Figure 1: CSC structures flexibility uses.

A LFM design can assume numerous configurations, since differentiated flexibility products can be traded, and since it must solve complex coordination problems among the roles involved, such as the local flexibility market operator (LFMO), the market participants, which include any FRP, the AGR, the RET and the DER providers, while defining the market clearing mechanism and a settlement procedures for the flexibility delivered [25]. The main contribution of this paper is on the possibility of using the integration of LFM and LEM under CSC to solve the energy transfer problem and to allocate the activated flexibility between the WSM agents using LEM energy transfers. It is important to consider that the proposal of energy transfers among BRP to solve the energy transfer problem is only one of the possible approaches. Other less regulated alternatives exist, such as leaving the BRP freely manage their risk [17]. As such, and even if the full design of the LFM considering all the communication and coordination problems from the grid operators to the activated DER [27] is not much relevant, it is still important to highlight the basic interactions and phases assumed to happen on the LFM considered in this paper:

- (i) Contracting on AGR level: Previously to any other phase, the AGR must constitute a portfolio of flexible DER who can be contracted on bilaterally negotiated deals. The LFMO is informed of these bilateral contracts and the AGR gains control over the DER assets if the flex is to be activated.
- (ii) Contracting on FRP level: FRP and AGR communicate within the LFMO to contract flexibility capacity. AGR does not trade DER flexibility individually, but the whole aggregated portfolio, profiting from the natural aggregation already existing in CSC.
- (iii) Flex requesting: The FRP, when in need of flexibility, requests it from the LFMO who calls the AGR to activate and deliver their DER portfolio according to the FRP needs. The LFMO intermediates the FRP call, but it is the AGR responsibility to optimize and compute the best possible activation and the DER deliveries of the FRP need according to the flexibility contracted and activated.
- (iv) Clearing and settlement: Activated contracts are cleared within the LFM rules considering the capacity contracted and the actual requested and delivered flexibility and their prices. The settlement considers the delivered amounts and the baseline methodology. The AGR are allocated, through CSC rules, the flexibility delivered by their DER while their respective RET maintains the baseline supply defined prior to the flexibility delivery.

As mentioned, an important aspect of the LFM is the baseline methodology, through which agents compute what would have been the DER delivery in the absence of flexibility activation [23]. Therefore, it is of fundamental importance to compute the amount of flexibility to be negotiated, activated, delivered, and settled. It concerns not only the DSO, who needs to assess the actual impact of the flexibility activation on the operation of its grid [28], but also all agents affected directly or indirectly by the flexibility activation. Setting up a baseline methodology can be complex and is subject to fraud, gaming opportunities, and other risks and some authors point to other solutions when setting up LFM [21]. However, many works focus on the design and application of baseline methods for each type of DER [19], [29]–[31] so, as detailed later, we assume that a baseline methodology is agreed among all participants in the form of a framework

contract that is used by the AGR and FRP on step (ii), above, and between AGR and DER owners on step (i). These assumptions are similar to the contractual model proposed in [17], where a framework contract is agreed between all parties setting a common baseline to compensate for indirect energy transfers.

One final note about the assumptions is that we only consider flexibility that is activated close to real time, and therefore after the end of the last intraday market session, leaving the RET with no opportunity to fix their WSM position.

Considering that in the LFM is being traded explicit flexibility measured with a common baseline methodology, and that AGR, when requested by their contracted FRP, activate flexibility from DER that have their own RET, a few important issues that this paper proposes to solve surge:

- The AGR activation of flexibility impacts the RET supplying the DER by generating imbalances to its expected supply corresponding to the flexibility activated [16], [17], since the activation of flexibility changes their normal energy behavior without the knowledge of their RET.
- The RET could be financially compensated for these activation impacts, reducing its imbalance risks and the associated costs, that in the end are paid by final customers.
- Energy settlement from activations on the LFM should also be settled on the WSM level.

These problems can be solved by integrating the LFM with a LEM that uses CSC rules to allocate local transactions in the proposed framework, as explained in the following section.

3. CSC REGULATIONS AND LEM INTEGRATION WITH WSM SETTLEMENT

The EU CSC and REC regulation and their energy sharing mechanisms rules are the spine-bone of our integrated LEM/LFM proposal since they allow WSM BRP to transfer energy among them by using allocation of energy through LEM trades. Figure 2 compares a simple ISC situation with a possible CSC structure. Under the ISC (left side), the 200 kWh surplus of prosumer B cannot be used to supply prosumer A that needs 300 kWh from its retailer. Under the CSC (right side), prosumer B supplies all its surplus to prosumer A that only needs 100 kWh from its retailer. This impacts the RET positions, since the RET of prosumer A supplies 200 kWh less, while the RET of prosumer B sees no surplus from prosumer B.

The fact that CSC allocations impact WSM BRP positions, like in this example, is the base of our proposal to transfer energy among the BRP to compensate for the activation of flexibility, where the energy transfers become LEM transfers, as explained later in section 4.

Figure 2: Basic CSC structure and effect of allocation on BRP positions

The way regulation defines how these energy allocations are operationalized, how the current CSC regulation allows these indirect energy transfers, and how LEM are integrated with the WSM settlement are explained in the remainder of this section. Relevant advances in the regulations in development are also pointed out. Indeed, further research on these topics will contribute to better policies and regulatory frameworks for better local DER integration and active participation in the energy system.

3.1. CSC REGULATIONS

Most reviewed CSC regulation schemes (see for example Spain [6], France [7], or Portugal [8], or [9] for a comparison of the Portuguese and Spanish regulations) are similar to the one represented in Figure 3, where the CSC structure composed of several DER can allocate energy from those who are injecting (generating) energy to the grid to those who are consuming. Allocation is performed by applying the AC, as shown in Figure 4, which is done by allocating to each DER the result of multiplying the energy injected to the grid within the community by the AC of each consuming DER. In case the CSC member is allocated less than its metered consumption, its RET supplies only the remaining amount. On the other hand, if he is allocated more than consumed, then its contracted AGR can buy its energy surplus [9]. Therefore, every DER that is likely to consume must hire a RET to provide energy when it cannot be supplied by the other community members. Note that, for the sake of simplicity, we are not differentiating CSC members from their DER, assuming they are the same. Also note that, under some regulations, the individual surpluses are aggregated and managed by the CSC Manager (as it is for the Portuguese case), which can sell it directly to the WSM or by means of and AGR. Finally, grid tariffs corresponding to the self-consumed energy usually consider only the tariffs corresponding to the grid used locally, and contracts to access the grids must be signed with the DSO and TSO for the final surplus to be traded in the WSM. In general, local transposition of EU directives may impose limits or relaxations to these general rules.

Figure 3: Basic CSC scheme.

In general, there are two types of AC to allocate energy among the DER of CSC structure, as shown in Figure 4. On the one side are the AC defined by pre-set rules, such as setting fixed AC values for each ISP, sharing the injection proportionally to the consumption or to the contracted power, or even applying hierarchical rules where a DER (or group of DERs) may use first the energy before sharing the remaining surplus with other. On the other side are the so-called dynamic AC that can be computed by the CSC Manager after all DER have already delivered their energy. Dynamic AC can be computed, for example, considering the ownership of the energy generated locally and the local transactions among CSC members, or even considering also hierarchical schemes.

Figure 4: Energy sharing by means of AC.

Initial regulations seemed to be more conservative by avoiding dynamic AC, but for example, they are already regulated in France and are being applied by ENEDIS [32], they are also proposed in the latest revision of the Portuguese electric system law [33], which considers also hierarchical rules, and are explicitly mention in the last EU market reform [4], that states the right of applying variable or dynamic methods to share energy, and even to share energy for self-consumption between prosumers without the need of creating energy communities.

Dynamic AC are a requisite for more advanced CSC schemes with LEM/LFM and can be used to integrate LEM within the WSM settlement, as described in [10]. However, so far, it seems that most regulations require that any DER has energy injected to the grid to be able to allocate energy to other DER of the CSC, which implies that AC must be between 0 and 1. However, if they were allowed to share energy regardless of their delivery, LEM designs could be even more flexible, allowing prosumers to trade energy in any situation that could provide them additional profit, contributing to the retail market competition as the authors already discussed in [10]. For instance, they could sell energy locally even when they are consuming by buying all the energy consumed and sold in the LEM from their RET, which would lead to negative AC values. As long as the sum of all AC equals 1, meaning that all energies bought and sold remain balanced, there does not seem to be a compelling reason not to allow it. In addition, matrix AC can also allow more complex CSC, for example with several connections to the grid at different voltage levels, allowing to specify the virtual paths of energy transaction. This way, grid tariffs can properly consider the voltage levels of the DER sharing energy, and the CSC could optimize these energy transactions to minimize the grid access tariffs. Matrix AC are going to be implemented in the Portuguese regulation for the dynamic AC sharing mechanism, as described in the on-going public consultation [34].

Therefore, for flexible energy allocation, policy makers should allow unrestricted AC that represent all local transactions as well as the ownership of the DER generation for each ISP. In addition, dynamic AC can be computed after the delivery of the energy, allowing post-delivery LEM where peers trade even after their consumption and generation takes place [11]. This type of LEM design contributes to customers' engagement since they do not have to forecast future consumption or generation profiles and commit them into forward contracts. Instead, they simply trade the amount of energy already delivered, as they currently do with their RET.

3.2. INTEGRATION OF LEM WITH THE WSM SETTLEMENT

So far, we explained how CSC regulation allows to transfer energy between prosumers in a LEM. This section explains the details of how the AC based energy sharing between these prosumers is integrated with the WSM settlement considering the main related roles of WSM agents, including the DSO, often responsible of measuring and allocating the self-consume energy, and the TSO responsible of the system balancing.

Indeed, an essential role of the TSO is to ensure that the system remains balanced at any time to keep the system frequency at its nominal value and preserve the quality of the grid service. This is done in real time, by constantly monitoring and forecasting the overall grid load and generation and activating reserves to solve imbalances. While the cost of reserving

regulation capacity for the automatic frequency restoration service (former secondary reserve) is usually paid by the consumers in many regulatory frameworks, the cost of the energy needed to keep the system balanced is shared among those BRP that cause these imbalances. The imbalance responsibility and costs are computed by the TSO after the delivery of the energy for each ISP and, therefore, its operation of reserves assets in real time.

Figure 5, using the roles identified in the USEF flexibility framework [17], proposes how the interactions among the main agents should be when the impact of CSC structures with local energy trades based on CSC dynamic AC is also considered.

Figure 5: WS settlement allocation and imbalance

As can be seen, the RET has a portfolio of prosumers under supply contracts for which it must predict their expected consumption, since it assumes the role of their BRP, and acquires these consumption in the WSM (step 0 in Figure 5). The metering data company (MDC), often the DSO itself, is responsible for metering the consumption of all clients (step 1). The allocation data responsible party (ARP), also often a role of the DSO, allocates the sum of the metered consumption, generation, and self-consumption in the CSC structure to the BRP and sends this information to the TSO (step 2). The WSM operator informs the TSO of all the energy contracted by the BRP in the WSM (step 3). Finally, the TSO compares the energy allocated to the RET with its global traded position (WSM previous position plus the ARP allocated energy) and calculates its imbalance (step 4), billing it according to its contribution to the grid imbalance costs (step 5).

In a CSC or a REC, the allocation of energy between its members directly impacts the RET balancing responsibility, but only after the energy is delivered, as described in Figure 5. Under this framework, the AC sent by the REC to the ARP is used to compute the allocation of the self-consumed energy to each BRP (that could be the RET in case of supply, or either an AGR or the same RET with the AGR role in case of surplus) in step 2. Since there is no need to send these ACs before the delivery because the WS settlement is entirely done after it, the REC should also be able to set the AC values after the delivery of energy, allowing LEM trades also after delivery in a post-delivery LEM as proposed in [11], [18], and described below. In fact, the TSO imbalance computation process takes at least several days, sometimes months, which provides a considerable time window for post-delivery local trades to happen. However, such AC are only possible in case regulation allows dynamic AC, as it is in the recent Portuguese regulation update [33], as soon as the Portuguese regulation entity ERSE adapts the current self-consumption rules [35] to the new regulatory proposals of [33].

The obligation of the RET to sell to their clients [19] means that there is usually no delivery commitment between final consumers and the RET in their supply contract. This concept remains the same in the post-delivery LEM. In both cases, customers do not have to commit to a previously defined-by-contract amount of energy to be supplied (forward contract), such as in the WSM. Customers just prosume and are billed for whatever they delivered. The main advancement of this integration of dynamic AC with the WSM settlement is that in a post-delivery LEM, RET's billing also considers the energy traded among peers, which is allocated through the dynamic AC as described in Figure 5. This implies that the post-delivery LEM contracts are also contracts with no delivery commitment, just like the traditional relationship between RET and their clients.

4. INTEGRATING FLEXIBILITY AND ENERGY LOCAL MARKETS

In this section we explain with examples how the dynamic AC are used to reflect the energy trades in a post-delivery LEM [11] and how this LEM can be integrated with the LFM to solve the issues discussed in section 2. The main principle is the fact that LEM transactions between prosumers with different RET lead to passive energy transfers between these RET in the WSM.

4.1. POST-DELIVERY LEM TRADES IMPACT ON WSM BRP IMBALANCE

Assuming a post-delivery LEM with dynamic AC, Figure 6 shows a prosumer B with a metered net surplus of 200 kWh in a given ISP that sells 150 kWh to prosumer A (step 1) reducing its surplus amount sold to its RET from 200 kWh to 50 kWh (step 2). Since prosumer A bought 150 kWh locally, it reduces its supply from its RET from 300 (its net consumption) to 150 kWh (step 2). Unlike the WSM, in the LEM there are no imbalance costs, but only each peers' opportunity costs of buying from and selling to the grid at a previously agreed price with their BRPs. Differences between prosumers' deliveries and their internally traded positions are settled with the BRP at the contractually defined price. It is the role of the peer's BRPs to settle imbalances with the TSO at wholesale level, as explained in section 3.2.

The LEM trade between prosumer A and B impacts their BRP balancing responsibilities in the form of a passive transfer on the same direction, as shown in step 3, since the RET of prosumer A's portfolio will consume an energy 150 kWh lower than forecasted on the WSM, while the RET of B will deliver 150 kWh more than forecasted (assuming their forecasts were accurate). LEM trades are post-delivery, so both RET cannot predict the transactions. In other words, assuming RET are initially balanced, RET A will see a positive imbalance of 150 kWh and RET B a negative imbalance of -150kWh with the TSO. Note that this could imply, in the medium-term, changes in the supply tariffs of the RET to their customers to account for the increased balancing risk, if no financial compensation is provided among BRPs.

Figure 6: Virtual transfer between BRPs in a post-delivery LEM

Since all prosumers are covered by a contract with their RET, the impact of the LEM trades on the overall system imbalance is null, and the increase of one BRP position is compensated for by a decrease in the other one. However, these LEM transactions do lead to imbalances in the prosumers' BRP position in the WSM due to the passive transfer problem illustrated in Figure 6, leading to financial costs for each BRP to deal with their imbalance. Since the passive transfer from LEM trade impact on the WSM imbalance is null, a compensation transfer rule between BRPs could be designed to avoid these unfair imbalances costs. This concept is proposed in the next section in the context of LFM.

4.2. INTEGRATING LEM AND LFM

As explained above, the delivery of distributed flexibility can be defined as a change in the expected consumption/production of a DER that is activated by a FRP for a specific period. On a basic level, two main pieces of information must be known: the expected delivery (the baseline) and the actual delivery after the flexibility activation request. While the latter is verified through metering data, the former requires more complex procedures that may need specific approaches for each DER type (for instance, load shifting, PV generation, storage). In typical WSM, the equivalent to the baseline for WSM agents is its traded position that results from all previous registered trading opportunities. Since all these trades are known by the WSM operator, it can easily compute the WSM agents' commitment that allows the TSO to compute their imbalances or to verify the flexibility provided.

However, LEM trades cannot be used to set baselines in a post-delivery LEM, since local contracts do not have delivery commitments and are signed even after the flexibility activation. Therefore, flexibility baseline methodologies must be used to estimate the DERs baselines to be interpreted as the DER's committed position before the flexibility is activated [36]. This often requires real time metering measurement and specific methods to estimate loads and forecast generation [19], [29], [31]. Since the baseline is the basis for verifying the flexibility provision, the method to compute it should be agreed amongst all agents that are impacted by the flexibility activation, which include the prosumer, AGR, RET and the FRP, and must be part of the flexibility purchase contract (FPC) and the flexibility need contract (FNC) on Figure 8.

Regarding the transfer of energy problem between the AGR and the RET, mentioned in section 2, also stated in [36], a framework contract applied in the LFM FPC can be used to solve it. Indeed, the activation of flexibility implies a passive transfer of energy between the RET and the AGR, a problem very similar to the example in Figure 6 discussed in section 4.1. If all parties agree on a baseline methodology, a transfer of energy in the opposite direction can be arranged to compensate for the passive transfer. We propose a methodology to integrate the LEM and the LFM where the energy transfer for the activated flexibility is automatically compensated for by a LEM transaction. The same solution can be used to nullify the imbalances created by LEM trades on BRP WSM settlement.

This automatic transaction is essentially the same one traded in the post-delivery LEM, i.e., a contract without delivery commitment. The AGR virtual prosumer trades with the activated prosumer the exact amount of delivered flexibility to generate a passive energy transfer on the opposite direction, as in Using the framework contract baseline, the prosumer's RET, who knows beforehand that the prosumer has a flexibility availability contract with the AGR, buys from the WSM the baseline amount to supply it in step 1. When the AGR activates a DR flexibility of 50 kWh reduction in consumption, a passive transfer of equivalent amount from the AGR to the RET happens. To compensate for this transfer, as explained above, an automatic transfer foreseen in the AGR-Prosumer FPC of 50 kWh from the prosumer to the AGR virtual prosumer is done in step 3, which generates a passive LEM transfer among the RET and the AGR which effectively nullifies the flexibility impact on the RET WSM position.

Figure 7: Using LEM trade to compensate LFM imbalance.

To apply this proposal using current regulations for CSC, some improvements are needed:

1. At first, the regulator should allow negative AC, as explained in section 3.2 [10] to allow prosumers providing flexibility to sell energy to the AGR virtual prosumer regardless of the amount of energy allocated to them. This assumption is important, since if negative AC are not allowed, the prosumer providing flexibility must have sufficient energy allocated to him before the activation to allocate the delivered flexibility to the virtual AGR (prosumer AGR in Figure 7), significantly reducing the flexibility liquidity in the LFM. For instance, a prosumer with no energy shared from the REC generation would not be able to transfer to the AGR a downwards flexibility.
2. Secondly, the regulator should allow the participation of virtual prosumers associated with the BRP in the CSC energy allocation mechanisms. As explained in Figure 5, for imbalance purposes, every prosumer is associated to a BRP through the allocation of each meter to its BRP. A virtual prosumer is basically a virtual nonphysical meter that is associated to a BRP under the CSC rules. As such, it always has zero metered consumption, but can have energy allocated internally, and even allocate energy to others if negative AC are allowed. Note that the associated BRP should assume commercial, financial and tariff responsibilities as any other prosumer.

Figure 8 shows this proposal to integrate the provision of flexibility in a LFM with a post-delivery LEM, including agents, roles, contracts, and an example of flexibility activation. On the right side are the WSM and agents who procure flexibility from the LFM, which is on the left side of the figure. These FRP may require flexibility for several reasons, such as balancing needs of BRP, grid constraints solving for DSO and TSO, and balancing reserves activation for TSO. To guarantee that the needed flexibility is provided, the framework contracts (FPC and FNC) adopt the baseline methodology for verification purposes. Even though DSO and TSO are not BRP, their flexibility activation impacts the BRP positions, and, therefore, must be accounted for in the settlement procedures, which could be done as described in the framework proposed.

This framework is inspired on the USEF contractual model [36], which distinguishes all roles relevant for activating distributed flexibility, as well as the contractual relations between the market participants, assuming the AGR and the RET sign a framework contract to transfer the energy delivered as flexibility, as explained ahead. However, unlike the USEF model, our proposal provides a practical solution to the contractual model transfer problem, integrated within a post-delivery LEM, which is also operationally feasible considering the current REC self-consumption regulation.

Amongst the main roles, we consider:

- FRP: such as the TSO and the DSO who may need flexibility for grid constrain solving, or WSM BRP (such as RET, AGR, generators or big consumers) who may wish to correct their WSM market position if conditions are favorable, or any other WSM agent with direct or indirect balancing responsibility that may require flexibility.
- AGR: with the role of aggregating DER and offering their flexibility to the FRPs.
- RET: role of supplying energy to the final consumers and prosumers.
- Prosumer: final consumer with DER behind its meter that may be used to offer flexibility.
- BSP: the Balancing Service Provider is a BRP who intermediate the flexibility service between the FRP and the AGR. As such, it specifies qualification, nomination, and activation procedures the AGR must comply to provide the FRP needed flexibility.

Figure 8: Local Flexibility Market roles and contracts

Regarding the contractual relations (the boxes with green text in Figure 8), from right to left, a FRP hires flexibility from the BSP in a contract tailored to its specific flexibility needs. The FRP might be a WSM BRP or a system operator. In any case, we assume it acts as a BRP for WSM settlement purposes. The BSP acquires flexibility through flexibility service contracts (FSC) with an AGR, who must comply with qualification, nominations and activation rules specified by the BSP for flexibility needs. The AGR procures flexibility from the prosumers by signing an LFM FPC, which incorporates the main framework that defines the baseline and energy transfer procedures (such as AGR-RET contracts) explained next.

In Figure 8, we assume a prosumer with an expected consumption E_B (baseline) equal to its expected metered delivery E_D^* (consumption, if positive) minus the expected energy E_G^* allocated from the REC generation ($E_B = E_D^* - E_G^*$) for a specific ISP. This prosumer's RET previously bought an amount E_B in the WSM corresponding to its expected to supply to this prosumer (step 0). When the FRP requests an amount of flexibility E_F (step 1), the BSP requests the activation of the same amount E_F to the AGR (step 2). The prosumer's DER delivers a flexibility ΔE_D (step 3), which may not correspond exactly to the value E_F requested, by modifying the energy delivery (metered) with respect to the baseline ($\Delta E_D = E_D - E_B$), where E_D is the metered prosumer's delivery. To avoid reducing the amount to be supplied by the RET and solve the problem of the passive transfer of energy, a LEM compensation transaction between AGR and RET is generated by the local market operator (step, 4) to compensate for this imbalance, resulting in a financial energy allocation transfer of ΔE_D between the activated prosumer and the virtual prosumer associated to the AGR. The RET, therefore, keeps supplying the same amount forecasted before the flexibility provision (the baseline $E_B = E_C - E_G$), not being impacted by the flexibility activation, and consequently, not needing any financial compensation for the flexibility activated by the AGR. The AGR, according to the FSC, transfers ΔE_D to the BSP (step 5), who delivers it to the FRP (step 6).

In our proposal, the transfer of energy is solved within the LEM (step, 4), Figure 8, with compensation transactions between the prosumer providing the flexibility and a virtual prosumer associated to the AGR. The LFMO must be informed of the flexibility activation, and based on the agreed baseline methodology, computes the flexibility delivered and generates a transaction between the parties. Therefore, the FPC isn't just a flexibility contract, but a contract that also activates a LEM energy compensation trade equal to the delivered flexibility.

Also note that, if the delivered flexibility differs from the requested by the FRP, the BSP will face an imbalance at the WSM equivalent to $(\Delta E_D - E_F)$. Its FSC with the AGR should include an imbalance cost transfer or even a penalty for any unfulfilled requested flexibility since this imbalance imposes costs to the BSP. Finally, let's remark that this allocation solves the problem of transfer of the flexibility energy between RET and AGR while settling the AGR position in the WSM FSC with the BSP, without the need for individual contacts among the involved RET and AGR.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

This paper presents an innovative integration of post-delivery LEM and LFM in CSC structures to solve the imbalance problem that involves BRP experience when local flexibility is provided to third parties. In addition, the approach could be fully implemented by current CSC regulations provided that minor improvements were considered. Due to the nature of flexibility products, where the product contracted is usually the difference between the energy delivered and a previously agreed baseline, the integration with post-delivery energy contracts, which do not have delivery commitment, requires an adequate definition of the player roles and their contractual relations. Amongst other roles, the LFM should define the baseline methodologies to be used by all agents and provide a framework for flexibility purchase contract between the AGR and the prosumers so that AGR can settle their activated resources portfolio with wholesale flexibility contracts and the RET be compensated for the change in its expected supply through LEM compensation trades. The framework contract separates the flexibility purchase contract into two elements: the provision of flexibility service, and the transfer of the delivered energy between the AGR and the RET through post-delivery LEM contracts.

This work contributes to a practical and implementable proposal of integration of a LFM with an easy-to-participate LEM market solution for prosumers, that uses the CSC regulation in Europe under development. For a full LEM and LFM implementation, some policy improvements are suggested, such as unrestricted AC (allowing negative values), matrixial allocation (to specify how each DER allocates the energy among the other DER), and the participation of virtual BRP prosumers. We also revise the main actor roles operating in the LFM and define the use of baseline framework contracts agreed by all participants as a condition for the energy allocation, which requires that all participants agree on a common baseline methodology, which may be difficult to implement. The baseline application for DER flexibility is still under research and several challenges regarding technical issues, but also proposals that avoid conflict of interest between agents, must be solved.

This work contribution is conceptual, but the authors are working on a simulation and pilot project [37] application of this, and other local energy and flexibility markets designs and integration frameworks with self-consumption regulations

towards simple but sound designs that contribute to engage final energy consumers in the energy markets. So far, few works have used CSC regulation to base LEM designs, and none other than the author's previous papers have proposed regulatory and policy improvements to improve the prospects of post-delivery LEM and LFM markets. The integration of CSC and local markets is a very new field of research, and proposals such as ours may contribute considerably to further research and development of LEM and LFM using the full potential of CSC.

While this proposal is general enough, limitations may come from two different dimensions. On the one hand, the energy transfers imply a more regulated interaction among the BRP supplying energy and providing flexibility, which may not strictly be needed. However, if not in place, BRP imbalance risks and costs may increase leading, in the end, to higher costs for the final prosumers to cover those risks. On the other hand, we deal with CSC regulation rules, but, although out of the scope of this work, a strong limitation comes from the current lack of LFM regulation. Indeed, even if the self-consumption regulations can already be adapted to include the proposed improvements, LFM regulation is still needed, as pointed out in section 2.1 of [38]. Therefore, the participation of DER in ancillary services, the lack of rules to allow DSO to activate flexibility, the need of clarifying the roles of TSO and DSO regarding distributed flexibility use, the proper incentives to TSO and DSO to plan and operate their grids considering flexibility, and baseline methodologies, among other topics, need to be further investigated and developed.

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